

Evaluation of Variability Resistance for Yellow Mosaic Virus between in Blackgram and Greengram

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Abstract

Mungbean yellow mosaic virus (MYMV) is a whitefly-transmitted major destructive virus affecting Blackgram and Green gram productivity in India. The objective of this research was to identify Blackgram and Green gram genotypes resistant against MYMV based on the phenotypic reaction and genotypic analysis. These results were confirmed through genotyping based on MYMV-resistance tagged molecular markers CEDG013, CEDG056, CEDG180 and CYR1. In addition to biochemical analysis on genotype resistance in the genotypes of each category (R-HS), effect of gamma irradiation on biochemical characteristics was studied. Results showed that the percentage of disease infection recorded positive significant association with phenol and total chlorophyll at both level, protein at genotypic level and negative significant association with sugars at both genotypic and phenotypic level. The new identified genotypes (resistant sources) can be utilized in the Blackgram and Green gram breeding programme for improving resistance to MYMV.

Introduction

Pulses, supplemented with cereals, provide a perfect mix of vegetarian protein of high biological value. India is the largest producer, importer and consumer of pulses, accounting for 25% of global production from 35% of global area under pulses. The productivity of pulses in India is less than half of the productivity levels in the USA and Canada, as the pulses are mainly grown under rain fed condition in India in the areas with high rainfall variability. The persistent and growing demand- supply gap is putting pressure on prices and this good source of vegetarian protein is turning in accessible to the poor. The production of pulses in India is caught in the vicious cycle of low and uncertain yields, poor per hectare returns resulting in farmers' least preference to grow pulses on irrigated and fertile parcel of land, thereby leading to unstable and low yields. Inadequate adoption of production technology, higher price volatility, production risk and low level of irrigation are the important influencing factors responsible for stagnation in the productivity of these crops.

The country would require 39 million tonnes of total pulses by 2050, which will require pulses production to grow at an annual rate of 2.2%. To fulfill the growing requirement, the country has to produce enough pulses as well as remain competitive to protect the domestic production. It is imperative to develop and adopt more efficient crop production technologies along with favourable policies and market support to encourage farmers to bring more area under pulses. In order to provide nutritional security to the poor masses relying on a vegetarian diet, making pulses affordable through boosting domestic production of pulses is the best alternative. In order to augment the supply of pulses to poor masses, under the current scenario supply through a public distribution system will not only distribute pulses to poor at affordable prices and enhance nutritional security, but will also lead to stabilize prices and provide a boost to the farmers through assured procurement. The lack of an assured market is one of the major issues in the poor performance of pulses.

As a result of significant increase in the area coverage and productivity of all major Pulses, total production of pulses during 2016-17 was estimated at 22.95 million tonnes which was higher by 3.70 million tonnes (19.22%) than the previous record production of 19.25 million tonnes achieved during 2013-14. Production of Pulses during 2016-17 was also higher by 5.32 million tonnes (30.16%) than their five years' average production. However the actual production in 2016-2017 was higher by 6.61 million tonnes (40.41%) than the previous year's production (22.95 million tonnes).

India is producing 14.76 million tons of pulses from an area of 23.63 million hectare, which is one of the largest pulses producing countries in the world. However, about 2-3 million tons of pulses are imported annually to meet the domestic consumption requirement. Thus, there is a need to increase production and productivity of pulses in the country by more intensive interventions.

To achieve target of additional production of pulses, it is necessary to concentrate efforts on five most important pulse crops depending upon their contribution in national production *viz.*, chickpea (39%), pigeonpea (21%), mungbean (11%), urdbean (10%), and lentil (7%).

Blackgram (*Vigna mungo* L. Hepper) also called urdbean is a member of the Asian *Vigna* crop group. It is a staple crop in central and South East Asia; however it is extensively used only in India and now grown in the Southern United States, West Indies, Japan and other tropics and subtropics.

In India, black gram occupies 12.7 percent of total area under pulses and contributes 8.4 per cent of total pulses production. India is the largest producer and consumer of black

gram which is cultivated in an area about 3.26 million hectares with a production of 1.76 million tonnes. Blackgram is a short duration, self-pollinated, diploid grain legume ($2n = 22$) with a small genome size estimated to be 0.56pg/1C (574 Mbp) (Gupta *et al.*, 2008).

The productivity of blackgram remains low due to biotic (mungbean yellow mosaic virus, powdery mildew and cercospora leaf spot) and abiotic stresses (drought, heat and preharvest sprouting). Among the various diseases limiting the blackgram and green gram productivity, Mungbean yellow mosaic virus (MYMV) was given special attention because of its severity and ability to cause yield loss up to 85% (Nene, 1972; Varma and Malathi, 2003).

Mungbean (*Vigna.radiata* (L.)Wilczek) is the most important (Rahman *et al.*, 2003). Besides being a rich source of protein, it maintains soil fertility through biological nitrogen fixation in soil and thus plays a vital role in furthering sustainable agriculture. It has gained importance mainly because of its wide use as a pulse crop with cheapest source of high quality easily digestible protein and also as a good source of green manure. It is consumed in the form of split pulse as well as whole pulse, which is an essential supplement of cereal based diet. The moong dal Khichdi is recommended to the ill or aged person as it is easily digestible and considered as a complete diet (Singh *et al.*, 2009). Likewise other pulse crops mungbean is a short duration grain legume crop with wide adaptability , low input requirements and deep root system, and proved an ideal for different crop rotations, intercropping, relay cropping and as catch crop (Devendra payasi *et al.*, 2010).

The area under pulses in India is around 1.38 lakh hectares with a production of 0.47 lakh tones. Greengram (*vigna radiata*), which is the third important pulse crop of India in terms of area cultivated and production next to gram and pigeon pea. In Tamil Nadu, greengram is cultivated in an area of 1.71 lakh hectares with an annual production of 0.55 lakh tones and productivity 321.64 kg ha⁻¹.

Area production and productivity of major pulses in India

(Area: lakh ha, Production: Lakh tonnes, Productivity: kg/ha)

Particulars	Area	Per cent	Production	Per cent	Productivity
Chickpea	73.7	38.71	58.9	48.28	799.19
Pegionpea	36.3	19.07	27.6	22.62	760.33
Mungbean	34.4	18.07	14	11.48	406.98

Uradbean	31	16.28	14	11.48	451.61
Lentil	15	7.88	9.5	7.79	633.33
Total	190.4	100.00	124	101.64	651.2

Many factors are responsible for the low productivity of blackgram ranging from plant ideotype to various biotic and abiotic stresses. Among the various diseases, Yellow Mosaic Disease (YMD) is given special attention because of its severity and ability to cause damage up to 100 percent. Among different gemini viruses, Mungbean Yellow Mosaic Virus (MYMV) is extensively studied as it infects five major leguminous crops e.g. black gram, green gram, french bean, pigeon pea and soybean. Whitefly-transmitted bipartite begomoviruses named as *Mungbean Yellow Mosaic India Virus* (MYMIV), *Mungbean Yellow Mosaic Virus* (MYMV), *Horsegram Yellow Mosaic Virus* (HgYMV) and *Dolichus Yellow Mosaic Virus* (DoYMV) are four distinct etiological agents of this disease in legume crops in India and other South Asian countries. Yield loss due to this disease varies from 5 to 100 percent depending upon disease severity, susceptibility of cultivars and population of whitefly (Nene, 1972; Singh, 1980; Rathi, 2002).

It has been confirmed that two virus species causing YMD are prevalent in Indian sub continent viz., Mungbean Yellow Mosaic India Virus (MYMIV) is commonly occurring in northern part of India and Mungbean Yellow Mosaic Virus (MYMV) is confined to Southern India. Existence of different species of yellow mosaic viruses changes the crop behaviour on nature of resistance exhibited by blackgram genotypes from southern to northern parts of India. The development of YMD resistant varieties along with disease screening is curtailed by the complexities of the viral strains, vector population, crop biology and environmental factors (Malathi and John, 2008).

Recently, it was reported that *Vigna mungo var. silvestris*, a wild species of black gram, was infected with YMV disease. The incidence of this wild species is reported to be 100% (Naimuddin *et al.*, 2011). Therefore identification of the etiological agent of YMD and making available genetic stock of *Vigna spp.* resistance to YMD, which is a prerequisite for breeding programmes for varietal improvement to achieve the effective and practical management of this disease at farmer’s field, is the most important goal.

Screening may be either on natural field conditions or through forced inoculation employing virulent vectors. In both the situations, vector population remains specific for the disease spread. Practical difficulties include climatic conditions that greatly affect the building

up of the vector population. If optimal conditions occur throughout the year, vector population will be present continuously. There is lack of uniform screening procedures and in many cases resistance is governed by recessive genes and hence significant delay in introgression of MYMV resistance gene in elite blackgram lines. The efficacy of transmission and behaviour of the whiteflies varies with the host genotypes, vector biotypes and growth conditions. Screening based on natural occurrence in the hot spot areas has not given consistent results. Hence, the plant breeders and pathologists are in need of biotechnological and molecular tools that can lead to the identification of MYMV resistant and susceptible genotypes.

In India, the virus causes more severe yellow mosaic disease in black gram than in mung bean in all of South Asia. Disease incidence as high as 100% in farmers fields is common in the Indian subcontinent, often resulting in considerable yield losses (Varma *et al.*, 1992). Soybean, blackgram, mung bean, moth bean, cowpea and a few other leguminous species have also been reported to be hosts of this virus. Singh (1980) reported that susceptibility was dominant over resistance with two recessive genes required for resistance.

GENETIC INHERITANCE OF MUNGBEAN YELLOW MOSAIC VIRUS

Inheritance of YMD resistance studies revealed that the resistance was controlled by two recessive genes (Verma, 1988, Amavasai *et al.*, 2004 and Singh *et al.*, 2006), a single recessive gene (Singh, 1977, Thaku., 1977, Saleem, 1998, Malik, 1986 Reddy, 1995 and Reddy, 2012) and complementary recessive genes (Shukla, 1985) and a dominant gene (Sandhu., 1985, Gupta *et al.*, 2005). Cayalvizhi *et al.* (2017) studied ninety F₂ genotypes developed from the cross made between KMG189 (MYMV-resistant) and VBN(Gg)2 (MYMV-susceptible), segregated in the mendelian single cross ratio 3S:1R; susceptibility of all the F₁s to MYMV suggested that the MYMV resistance in mungbean is governed by a single recessive gene.

EFFECT OF GAMMA IRRADIATION ON BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Different types of electromagnetic radiation are available such as gamma irradiation, X irradiation, visible light UV irradiation. Radiation has a different range of energies and frequencies. Compared to other radiations, gamma irradiation is considered as more energetic form of radiation nearly 10 KeV to several 100 KeV and it has more penetrable power compared to alpha and beta irradiation. The relationship between growth of irradiated plants and dose of gamma irradiation has been manifested by investigating the morphological changes and seedling growth of the irradiated plants. No significant morphological aberrations were observed (Yasmin *et al.*, 2022) in the phenotype of the plants irradiated with relatively

low doses (1–5 Gy) of gamma rays. Gamma radiation affects the plant growth and induces change in genetic level, physiological, biochemical and morphological nature of the cells. Gamma radiation induces biochemical changes and breaks the bond in between chains, cross-linking in DNA molecules and protein molecules. Protein, carbohydrate and vitamins are necessary for the seedling development. Based on the gamma radiation doses, various morphological and biochemical characters alter and induce and stimulate seedling growth and enhanced germination.⁶⁵ In plants, gamma irradiation effects are determined based on the amino acids changes and are essential for human diets. Increased gamma radiation affects the quality of reducing sugar, starch content, carotenoids and other organic nature of the plant cell commonly used in understanding the plant growth and development. Carotenoids are generally present in plant chloroplast and are also useful to protect the chlorophyll from photo-damage and also interlink with other major metabolic function.

ANALYSES OF BIOCHEMICAL ALTERATIONS INDUCED BY GAMMA IRRADIATION BY FTIR SPECTROSCOPY

Alteration and changes of biochemical profiles are commonly characterized by the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). FTIR is also useful to identify the functional groups and it may be used to identify the unknown structure and composition of chemical groups and intensity of absorption spectra which associate with molecular composition of chemical compositions. Generally, FT-IR method is used to measure the vibrations of chemical bonds and functional groups and it generates the spectrum for biochemical and metabolite of the samples based on the “fingerprint”. Based on the infrared spectrum of plant samples, the minor and major changes present in primary and secondary metabolites are also detected.

FTIR spectroscopy is useful to monitor the modification in the structural and properties of biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, protein, carbohydrate, lipids and other plant cell and tissues. FTIR spectroscopy is the emerging technique for understanding and studying the biochemical alterations in plants. FTIR micro spectroscopy with multivariate data analysis is used to differentiate the spectral fingerprint of biochemical changes in plant tissues. Gamma irradiation induces oxidative stress due to the over production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) including superoxide radicals, hydroxyl radicals and hydrogen peroxides. Due to the overproduction of ROS, it reduces the antioxidants in plant tissues. Biotic and abiotic stresses induce ROS by the action of NADPH oxidase which triggers plant defence mechanism against various stress conditions and it enhances the tolerance capacity of plants to different stress environment and pathogens. Gamma irradiation induced more free radicals at increasing doses

of gamma irradiation on seeds which affect the growth in black gram. Effect of mutagens on quantitative (agronomic) traits of crop plants: Due to gamma irradiation stress, M1 generation results reduced rate of seedling germination, meanwhile in M2 generation, low rate of mutation effects was noticed in seed germination. This reduced seedling germination rate in M2 generation mainly due to the reduced effect of mutation in second generation as well as in DNA repair mechanism in plant tissues.⁷⁴In M1 generation, the increased gamma irradiation doses reduce the agronomic and morphological traits. However, in M2, M3 and M4 generations, significant enhancements were recorded in morphological and yield traits reported in various crops. The yield parameters such as number of clusters per plant, seed per plant and seed yield per plant were moderate to higher at higher gamma radiation.

GENETIC DIVERSITY IN BLACKGRAM

At Annamalai University the genetic divergence was estimated on the basis of D^2 values and 40 genotypes of blackgram under study were grouped into six clusters by Tocher's method. The relative contribution of individual characters towards the expression of genetic diversity was estimated over character wise D^2 value. The inter-cluster distances were greater than intra-cluster distances, revealing that considerable amount of genetic diversity existed among the accessions. The characters namely single plant seed yield, percentage disease infection, number of clusters per plant and number of pods per plant contributed more than 90% towards divergence. Hence, these characters appeared most important for check indices. Among this Character which expressed higher genetic advance may be exploited as they respond better for selection (Malarkodi, 2018) (Unpublished).

MARKER ASSISTED ELUCIDATION OF VARIABILITY FOR YMV IN BLACKGRAM

Marker assisted indirect selection of resistant genotypes using linked markers has been reported as an effective breeding approach for developing YMV resistant cultivars in blackgram. It is assuming increased importance due to lack of uniform field screening procedure as well as difficulty in direct selection due to complex virus, vector, host and environmental interaction (Souframanien and Gopalakrishna, 2006). Few molecular markers linked with YMD resistance were identified (Basak *et al.*, 2004; Souframanien and Gopalakrishna, 2006; Maiti *et al.*, 2011). Yet, validation of such markers becomes an essential criterion with regard to the intricate disease nature.

Among various DNA marker systems, SSR markers are considered the most ideal marker for genetic studies because they are multi-allelic, abundant, randomly and widely

distributed throughout the genome, co-dominant that could differentiate plants with homozygous or heterozygous alleles, simple to assay, highly reliable, reproducible and could be applied across laboratories, and amenable for automation. Microsatellites or Simple Sequence Repeats (SSR) are DNA sequences with repeat lengths of a few base pairs. Variation in the number of repeats can be detected with PCR by designing primers for the conserved DNA sequence flanking the SSR. As molecular markers, SSR combine many desirable marker properties including high levels of polymorphism and information content, unambiguous designation of alleles, even dispersal, selective neutrality, high reproducibility, co-dominance, rapid and simple genotyping assays. Microsatellites have become the molecular markers of choice for a wide range of applications in genetic mapping and genome analysis paternity determination and pedigree analysis, gene and quantitative trait locus analysis and marker-assisted breeding.

Investigations at Annamalai University using molecular Markers for YMV resistance on blackgram revealed that nine out of fifteen markers (63.2%) showed polymorphic bands among the genotypes tested. Out of the remaining six markers five markers were bi-allelic producing two distinct alleles among the genotypes while one marker was mono-allelic showing a dominant allele pattern. Polymorphic information content of the nine polymorphic markers ranged from 0.30 to 0.65. Four markers namely CEDG013, CEDG056, CEDG180 and CYR1 had PIC values above 0.5 and hence can be considered as informative markers for YMV screening (Malarkodi, 2018) (Unpublished).

In another study involving twenty six genotypes of blackgram we concluded that twelve out of nineteen markers (63.2%) showed polymorphic bands among the genotypes tested. Eight markers were biallelic producing two distinct alleles among the genotypes while four markers were mono-allelic showing a dominant allele pattern. Percentage polymorphism was highest in CEDG 059 (55.8%). The genetic distance estimated using DICE dissimilarity co-efficient indicated highest divergence of 1.0 between VBN 8 and AUBG 17 and between VBN 8 and AUBG 19. The dendrogram showed four apparent clusters based on marker allele distribution. Single marker analysis with CEDG092 revealed that genotypes AUBG 6, VBN4 and VBN8 carried the positive alleles for YMV resistance and the allele for susceptibility was present in AUBG12, AUBG15, AUBG17, AUBG19.

MUNGBEAN

D² ANALYSIS

The Mahalanobis D² analysis as a potent tool for estimating the genetic diversity and it

provides a rational basis for selection of parents for hybridization programme. The present investigation, eleven economic traits were studied in forty five genotypes were subjected to D² analysis. By the application of non-hierarchical clustering technique the genotypes grouped into five clusters in S1, eight clusters in S2 and pooled analysis.

Among the clusters the maximum numbers of genotypes were recorded in cluster I and II in S1 and cluster in S2 followed by in cluster in pooled analysis.

The intra cluster distance was maximum in cluster IV in S1 and pooled analysis; while it was cluster III in S2. The divergence within the cluster indicates the divergence among the genotypes in the same cluster. The minimum intra cluster distance in cluster V and VI in S1, While it was cluster IV in S2 and cluster III in pooled analysis.

The inter cluster distance was maximum between cluster III and V and minimum between clusters I and VI in S1. In S2, the maximum inter cluster distance was exhibited by cluster V and VI and minimum between cluster VI and V. In pooled analysis the maximum inter cluster distance was observed in between cluster III and VII and it was minimum between cluster II and III. The inter cluster distance was higher than intra cluster distance.

CLUSTER MEAN

The maximum cluster mean value for single plant seed yield was exhibited by cluster IV in S1, while it was cluster VIII in S2 and cluster VII in pooled analysis. Days to 50% flowering recorded lowest mean value in cluster VI in S1, cluster IV in S2 and cluster in VIII in pooled analysis. Cluster II recorded minimum plant height in S1, S2 and pooled analysis.

The maximum number of branches per plant was exhibited by cluster III in S1, cluster V in S2 and cluster I in pooled analysis. Number of clusters per plant was higher in cluster III in S1, cluster VIII in S2 and cluster VI in pooled analysis. Cluster III recorded higher number of pods per cluster in S1, cluster VIII in S2 and cluster in VI in pooled analysis. The maximum number of pods per plant was exhibited by cluster III in S1 followed by cluster V in S2 and cluster VI in pooled analysis. Pod length recorded highest mean value in cluster VI in S1 and cluster VIII in S2 and pooled analysis. Cluster IV showed highest cluster mean value in S1, followed by cluster III in S2 and cluster II pooled analysis. Minimum value of percentage of disease infection was recorded in cluster I in S1, cluster VI in S2 and cluster VII in pooled analysis. Cluster VI recorded highest hundred seed weight in S1 and pooled analysis, while it was cluster VIII in S2.

VARIATION BASED ON BIOCHEMICAL MARKERS BIOCHEMICAL MARKER

Among the forty five genotypes, twenty five genotypes scored and selected based on

percentage of disease infection from pooled analysis.

PROTEIN

Protein content of genotypes varied from 0.18 to 0.31 mg/g. The minimum was observed in genotype G6 (0.18 mg/g) and the maximum was observed in genotype G39 (0.31 mg/g). Out of twenty five genotypes, four genotypes recorded higher significant mean value than the general mean of 0.23 mg/g. The protein content is higher in susceptible genotype than the resistant genotype.

PHENOLS

The phenol content of genotypes ranged from 0.75 to 4.67 mg/g. The minimum phenol content was observed in G3 (0.75 mg/g). The maximum was observed in genotype G20 and G39 (4.67 mg/g). Out of twenty five genotypes, twelve genotypes registered higher significant mean value than the general mean of 2.60 mg/g. The phenol content is higher in susceptible genotype than resistant genotype.

SUGARS

The sugar content was ranged from 2.70 to 8.67 mg/g. The minimum sugar content was observed in genotype G15 (2.70 mg/g) and the maximum was observed in genotype (8.67 mg/g). Out of twenty five genotypes, seven genotypes recorded higher significant mean value than the general mean of 4.83 mg/g. The sugar content is higher in resistant than the susceptible genotype.

TOTAL CHLOROPHYLL

Total chlorophyll content of genotypes varied from 1.40 to 2.13 mg/g. The minimum was observed in genotype G20 (1.40 mg/g) and the maximum total chlorophyll G19 (2.13 mg/g). Out of twenty five genotypes, seven genotypes registered higher significant mean value than the general mean of 1.80mg/g. Increased in total chlorophyll in resistant genotype than susceptible genotype.

CORRELATION STUDIES

Estimates of correlation between percentage of disease infection and isozymes component characters in greengram are presented in the table.

The protein had significant positive association with phenol (0.402), total chlorophyll (0.470) and percentage of disease infection (0.456) at genotypic level. The phenol recorded positive and significant association with percentage of disease infection (0.768 and 0.787) and negative significant association with sugars (-0.473 and -0.486) at both phenotypic and genotypic levels. The sugars had negative significant association with percentage of disease infection (-0.454 and -0.456) at both levels. The total chlorophyll recorded positive significant

association with percentage of disease infection (0.513 and 0.553) at both levels.

The percentage of disease infection recorded positive significant association with phenol and total chlorophyll at both level, protein at genotypic level and negative significant association with sugars at both genotypic and phenotypic level.

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